

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**BURN WOUND INFECTIONS TREATMENT &
MANAGEMENT IN PAKISTAN**¹Dr Yasir Saleem, ²Dr Madiha Tariq, ³Dr Jahadullah¹Department of Burn and Plastic Surgery Affiliated Hospital of Qinghai University
Xining China²Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology Affiliated Hospital of Qinghai University
Xining China³University College Medicine and Dentistry, The University of Lahore**Article Received:** January 2020 **Accepted:** February 2020 **Published:** March 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To analyze the treatment options for burn infections and determine the antibiotic sensitivity and resistance pattern and antibiotic consumption in defined daily dose.

Place and Duration: In the Department of Burn and plastic surgery, Mayo Hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Materials and methods: Patients with burns admitted between March 2018 and March 2019 were selected for the study. Patient demographics, total burn area (TBSA), burns, treatment table, days of hospitalization, and antibiotic susceptibility / resistance profile were recorded. The cumulative susceptibility / resistance pattern (in percent) of microorganisms isolated against various antibiotics was calculated based on the culture sensitivity reports. The total use of the antibiotic in burn patients was calculated as DDD / 100 BD using the antibiotic consumption calculator - WHO ABC Calc version 3.1. The patient additionally were planned for daily debridement and papaya dressing.

Results: Thermal burns (81.8%) were the main cause of burns in 159 patients. The most commonly prescribed antibiotic was cefoperazone-sulbactam (54.7%), followed by amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (34%). In total, 82 bacterial isolates were obtained, among which the most common organism was *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (31.6%). *P. aeruginosa* was sensitive to rifampin and erythromycin but was resistant to clindamycin. 90% of the infections in patients were managed conservatively with appropriate antibiotics after culture sensitivity and 10 percent needed debridement and papaya dressing for wounds.

Conclusion: Appropriate antibiograms will facilitate the conceptualization and development of drug policy to improve burn treatment results. Appropriate preventive and therapeutic measures should be taken to provide social education and quality medical care to reduce the incidence of burn patients and improve survival outcomes.

Keywords: Sensitivity to antibiotics, burns, specific daily dose in burns, assessment of drug use

Corresponding author:**Dr Yasir Saleem,**

Department of Burn and Plastic Surgery

Affiliated Hospital Of Qinghai University Xining China

QR code

Please cite this article in press Yasir Saleem et al, *Burn Wound Infections Treatment & Management In Pakistan.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(03).

INTRODUCTION:

Burns are tissue damage from heat, electricity, sunlight, chemicals, radiation or friction. Burns are classified by body depth and severity¹⁻². Depth is characterized by first, second- and third-degree burns. Severity is based on total body surface area (TBSA). Antimicrobial resistance in burn wound pathogens is a problem for doctors, especially due to the emergence of various resistant bacterial strains³⁻⁴. Wound burn infection is the most common cause of morbidity and causes 75% mortality⁵⁻⁶. Therefore, proper treatment plan should be devised to every patient to reduce the risk of infections.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A retrospective observational study was conducted in the Department of Burn and plastic surgery, Mayo Hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020 among 159 patients with varying degrees of burns; Burn patients admitted between March 2018 and March 2019 were selected for the study. They underwent a retrospective review based on their medical records. Demographic data, treatment table as well as antibiotic sensitivity and patient resistance profile were recorded on a specially prepared registration form. Nominal data is expressed as frequency and percentage. The data were analyzed as follows: The cumulative sensitivity and resistance pattern of the microorganisms isolated against various antibiotics was calculated based on the culture susceptibility report and given as a percentage. Total antibiotic consumption was calculated as the daily dose defined using the antibiotic consumption calculator - WHO ABC Calc version 3.1 (WHO Drug Statistics Methodology Collaboration Center, Oslo). Data entry and statistical analysis were performed using SPSS version 20 (IBM Corporation, New York, USA) and MS Excel.

RESULTS:

Thermal burns (81.8%) were the main cause of burns in the studied population. Patient surfaces were classified according to TBSA, of which the median is 23% TBSA. Treatment of burn patients: the most commonly prescribed antibiotic was cefoperazone-sulbactam (54.7%) followed by amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (34%). 90% of the infections in patients were managed conservatively with appropriate antibiotics after culture sensitivity and 10 percent needed debridement and papaya dressing for wounds.

Antimicrobial sensitivity / resistance pattern and antibiotic pattern in burned patients

In total, 12 microorganisms were obtained from 82 positive cultures. The most common isolated microorganisms were *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

(31.6%) followed by *Klebsiella Pneumoniae* (19.4%), *Acinetobacter* (12.3%) and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) (10.3%) [Table 1].

Sensitivity / resistance profiles of isolated organisms.***Pseudomonas aeruginosa***

It is 100% sensitive to tetracycline, imipenem, linezolid, rifampin and teicoplanin, and then less sensitive to colistin (92.3%), aztreonam (3.7%) and is highly resistant to clindamycin, cloxacillin, ticarcillin-tazobactam and erythromycin (100%).

Table 1: List of isolated microorganisms.**Table 1: List of microorganisms isolated**

Microorganisms	n (%)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	49 (31.6)
<i>Klebsiella Pneumoniae</i>	30 (19.4)
<i>Acinetobacter</i>	19 (12.3)
MRSA	16 (10.3)
<i>Enterobacter</i>	11 (7.1)
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	11 (7.1)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	8 (5.2)
MSSA	5 (3.2)
<i>Enterococcus</i>	3 (1.9)
<i>Citrobacter</i>	1 (0.6)
<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	1 (0.6)
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	1 (0.6)

MSSA: Methicillin-sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus*,
MRSA: Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*

Klebsiella Pneumoniae

It is very sensitive to vancomycin (100%) and is resistant to amoxicillin, ampicillin, cefepime and ticarsilinzobactam (100%).

Acinetobacter was 100% sensitive to colistin, then resistant to cefoperazone-sulbactam (92.8%) and netilmicin (81.8%) and 100% resistant to amoxicillin, ampicillin, ceftazidime, cefuroxime, chloramphenicol, piperacillin and tobramycin.

Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*

It is 100% sensitive to colistin, linezolid, rifampicin, teicoplanin and vancomycin, as well as 100% resistant to amoxicillin, ceftazidime, cefuroxime, piperacillin-tazobactam and erythromycin.

Enterobacter

100% susceptible to amikacin, ceftriaxone, ciprofloxacin, netilmicin, cefoperazone-sulbactam, piperacillin-tazobactam and imipenem, but 100% resistant to amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ampicillin, ceftazidime, cefazoline, ceftamide, anchor

Proteus mirabilis

Cefepim, colistin, imipenem and ceftazidime were 100% sensitive, followed by cefoperazone-

sulbactam (85.7%). It is 100% resistant to amoxicillin, amikacin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ampicillin, cefazolin, ceftriaxone, cefuroxime, co-trimoxazole, gentamicin, netilmicin, piperacillin and tobramycin.

Escherichia coli

Piperacillin-tazobactam was 100% sensitive to colistin, imipenem and tetracycline. It is resistant to amoxicillin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ampicillin, cefazoline, ceftazidime, piperacillin, tobramycin, aztreonam and cefepime (100%).

Methicillin-sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* was very sensitive (100%) to amikacin, ceftriaxone, colistin, tetracycline, linezolid, teicoplanin and vancomycin (100%) and was resistant to amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, erythromycin, cloxacillin (100%).

Enterococci

Imipenem was very sensitive (100%) to tetracycline, linezolid, teicoplanin, vancomycin and less sensitive to chloramphenicol, ampicillin and gentamycin. Complete resistance (100%) was observed to amoxicillin, amikacin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, cefazoline, ceftriaxone, cefuroxime, ciprofloxacin, co-trimoxazole,

netilmicin, tobramycin, aztreonam, piperacromycin-t.

Citrobacter

The species showed complete sensitivity (100%) to ceftriaxone, co-trimoxazole, aztreonam, cefoperazonesulbactam, piperacillin-tazobactam, imipenem, and showed complete resistance (100%) to amikacin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ampicillin, cefazolin, ceftazidime, cefuroxime, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and netilmicin.

Klebsiella oxytoca

Amikacin, ceftriaxone, ciprofloxacin, netilmicin, cefoperazone-sulbactam, piperacillin-tazobactam were very sensitive (100%). However, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ampicillin, cefazolin, ceftazidime, cefuroxime, corticoxazole, gentamicin, aztreonam, colistin were resistant to it (100%).

Proteus vulgaris

It was 100% sensitive to cefoperazone-sulbactam, piperacillin-tazobactam and imipenem and 100% amoxicillin, amikacin, amoxicillin avulanic acid, cefazolin, ceftriaxone, cefuroxime, ciprofloxacin, cotrimoxazole, gentamicin and netilmicin. Total antibiotic consumption was technically measured with DDD / 100 BD.

Table 2: Top ten antibiotics used in burns patients

ATC code	Route	Antimicrobial agent	DDD WHO (g)	DDD/100 BD	Prescription (n)	Units
J01D012	Parenteral	Cefoperazone	4	40.21	101	50.5
J01GB07	Parenteral	Netilmicin	3.5	33.94	28	93.3
J01CR02	Parenteral	Amox/clav	3	18.48	45	37.5
J01XB01	Parenteral	Colistin	3	17.18	17	8.5
J01DH02	Parenteral	Meropenem	2	16.36	19	19
J01CG01	Parenteral	Sulbactam	1	10.43	8	16
J01GB06	Parenteral	Amikacin	1	9.21	24	12
J01XX08	Parenteral	Linezolid	1.2	8.94	23	38.3
J01CR02	Oral	Amox/clav	1	5.35	8	12.8
J01CF02	Parenteral	Cloxacillin	2	4.38	4	16
J01CA01	Parenteral	Ampicillin	2	3.44	4	16
J01DH51	Parenteral	Imipenem	2	2.35	10	20

DISCUSSION:

A retrospective observational study involved 159 patients with burns in 2018. Data from medical records was collected and analyzed, with thermal burns being the most common. In our study, sepsis accounted for 50% of deaths, and burns reflect the results of Chawli *et al.* Highlighting septic shock, primary shock and oligomeric shock as the most common causes of death in patients. Twelve different microorganisms were isolated from burn patients⁷⁻⁸. The most common organism causing

burn infection from 82 positive microbial growths was *P. aeruginosa* (31.6%) followed by *Klebsiella Pneumoniae* (19.4%), *Acinetobacter* (12.3%) and *MRSA* (10.3%). A study by Saaq with 95 positive microbial growth and highest isolation, *P. aeruginosa* (35.29%) and *K. pneumoniae* (20.58%), methicillin sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* (18.62%), *Proteus mirabilis* (9, 80%), *Escherichia coli* (6.86%), and the lowest is *acinetobacter* (6.86%).

Table 3: Ten least antibiotics used in burns patients

ATC Code	Route	Antimicrobial agent	DDD WHO (g)	DDD/100 BD	Prescription (n)	Units
J01XA02	Parenteral	Teicoplanin	0.4	0.30	1	2.5
J01DB04	Parenteral	Cefazolin	3	0.28	1	1
J01GB03	Parenteral	Gentamicin	0.24	0.28	1	1.3
J01MA02	Oral	Ciprofloxacin	1	0.25	2	4
P01AB02	Oral	Tinidazole	2	0.17	1	1.3
J01XA01	Parenteral	Vancomycin	2	0.17	2	4
J01DB05	Oral	Cefadroxil	2	0.16	1	2
J01FA10	Oral	Azithromycin	0.3	0.13	1	2
J01DE01	Parenteral	Cefepime	2	0.07	1	0.5
J01DC02	Parenteral	Cefuroxime	3	0.04	5	20

According to the report of Dash et al. *P. aeruginosa*, the most common isolate, it was resistant to imipenem (100%) and piperacillin-tazobactam, which showed a similar sensitivity / resistance profile showing that *P. aeruginosa* is less resistant to piperacillin-tazobactam and imipenem. *P. aeruginosa* is the main organism that causes nosocomial infections and is the most common isolate with the highest resistance profile in our study population⁹⁻¹⁰. Ozer et al. It showed that *P. aeruginosa* is the cause of nosocomial infections. *P. aeruginosa*, resistant to a wide range of antibiotics, produces plasmid-mediated beta-lactamases (e.g. cephalosporinases, which are more likely to hydrolyze cephalosporins than penicillin), which provides a robust mechanism for cephalosporin resistance (81.2%). Resistance to aminoglycoside (75.03%) in *P. aeruginosa* includes plasmid-mediated resistance due to the presence of aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes that are often observed during nosocomial infection outbreaks¹¹⁻¹². *P. aeruginosa* can also modify aminoglycosides by acetylation, phosphorylation or adenylation. *Proteus vulgaris* is the least isolated organism (0.6%) that is highly resistant to amoxicillin-clavulanate and ampicillin (100%) associated with a study by Sewunet, where *P. vulgaris* has high resistance. amoxicillin-clavulanate and ampicillin. Parenteral cefoperazone, a pattern of antibiotic use with third generation cephalosporin, showed the highest intake (40.21) followed by netilmicin (33.94), amoxicillin-clavulanate (18.48). Parenteral cefuroxime (0.04) consumption was lower.

Overall consumption of third generation cephalosporins was higher than the use of first and second generation cephalosporins¹³⁻¹⁴. Then aminoglycosides were used. Of the 361 prescriptions contained in this study, the average number of antibiotics prescribed was 2.5, and the range of 1 to 8 antimicrobials was comparable to the study by Padwal et al. Third generation cephalosporins were the most commonly prescribed antibiotic cephalosporins¹⁵. Our study population was similar to the study by Theron and Nel, in which third generation cephalosporins ended their useful role in the treatment of extensive

sepsis caused by burn injuries. The most common antibiotics used to prevent eye infections include fluoroquinolones, mainly ciprofloxacin, which moisturize the eye and prevent infection.

CONCLUSION:

The use of antibiotics requires the coordination of doctors with a multidisciplinary healthcare team of clinical pharmacists, microbiologists and nurses to ensure optimal use of antimicrobials in burn patients. Infections are a serious problem in burns and in very resistant *P. aeruginosa* strains, which appear to be the most common causing organism. Hospitals should set up a surveillance system that records resistance / vulnerability patterns as well as burn infections. This examination should be repeated periodically and an antibiogram should be developed that the hospital should formulate an effective antibiotic policy.

REFERENCES:

1. Choudhary, V., Kumar, P., Kumar, P., Kumar, P. and Kumar, S., 2019. Epidemiological study of burn admissions in a tertiary burn care center of Bihar, India. *Indian Journal of Burns*, 27(1), p.63.
2. Bailey, M.E., Sagiraju, H.K.R., Mashreky, S.R. and Alamgir, H., 2019. Epidemiology and outcomes of burn injuries at a tertiary burn care center in Bangladesh. *Burns*, 45(4), pp.957-963.
3. Laughon, S.L., Gaynes, B.N., Chrisco, L.P., Jones, S.W., Williams, F.N., Cairns, B.A. and Gala, G.J., 2019. Burn recidivism: a 10-year retrospective study characterizing patients with repeated burn injuries at a large tertiary referral burn center in the United States. *Burns & trauma*, 7(1), pp.s41038-019.
4. Khan, A., Parikh, M., Minhajuddin, A., Williams, T., Abrams, R., Kandil, E. and Ambardekar, A., 2020. Opioid prescribing practices in a pediatric burn tertiary care facility: Is it time to change?. *Burns*, 46(1), pp.219-224.
5. Saraswat, B., Yadav, A. and Maheshwari, K.K., 2019. EPIDEMIOLOGY AND OUTCOMES OF ELECTRIC BURN INJURY

- AT TERTIARY CARE CENTER IN JODHPUR, RAJASTHAN. *International Journal of Medical and Biomedical Studies*, 3(6).
6. Elrouby, M. and Abdelsalam, A., 2020. Epidemiological Study of Mass Casualties at A Tertiary Burn Center in Ain-Shams University: Management and Outcomes. *The Egyptian Journal of Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery*, 43(3), pp.365-369.
 7. Kishanrao, D.V. and Wadde, S.K., 2019. Trends of admission and deaths of burn patients (2000 to 2016) in a tertiary care hospital of Maharashtra: a time series analysis. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 6(11), p.4972.
 8. Pratap Duggirala, D., Sarabahi, S., Tiwari, V.K. and Annapareddy, S.N.R., 2019. To evaluate how early operative intervention will increase the chances of limb survival in electrical burns-At a tertiary Burn care centre. *International Journal of Surgery*, 3(4), pp.448-453.
 9. Noor, D.M., Wicaksana, A., Fauzi, A.R. and Seswandhana, R., 2020. Comparison between revised Baux score and abbreviated burn severity index as a predictor of mortality in burn patients at a tertiary care center in Yogyakarta, Indonesia. *European Journal of Plastic Surgery*, 43(1), pp.53-58.
 10. Agbenorku, P., Agbenorku, M., Bayuo, J. and Asare, N.Y.O., 2019. Epidemiology and outcome of suspected inhalational burn injury in a Ghanaian tertiary hospital. *Burns Open*, 3(2), pp.45-50.
 11. Matthews, M.R., Van Sant, L.M., Bollenbach, S.E., Swanson, S.D., Hollingworth, A.K. and Foster, K.N., 2019. Why trauma must trump burn injuries: The spectre of missed injuries. *Burns Open*, 3(3), pp.112-115.
 12. Elmasry, M., Steinvall, I., Olofsson, P. and Sjöberg, F., 2020. Admission of Burn Patients to the Burn Center Including Burn Wound Evaluation. In *Handbook of Burns Volume 1* (pp. 171-179). Springer, Cham.
 13. Baier, C., Ipaktchi, R., Schwab, F., Smith, A., Liu, X., Ebadi, E., Limbourg, A., Mett, T.R., Bange, F.C. and Vogt, P.M., 2019. Universal decolonization with octenidine: First experiences in a tertiary burn intensive care unit. *Burns Open*, 3(1), pp.8-11.
 14. Yagnik, K.J., Kalyatanda, G., Cannella, A.P. and Archibald, L.K., 2019. Outbreak of *Acinetobacter baumannii* associated with extrinsic contamination of ultrasound gel in a tertiary centre burn unit. *Infection Prevention in Practice*, 1(2), p.100009.
 15. Goswami, P., Sahu, S., Singodia, P., Kumar, M., Tudu, T., Kumar, A. and Sinha, P.K., 2019. Early Excision and Grafting in Burns: An Experience in a Tertiary Care Industrial Hospital of Eastern India. *Indian Journal of Plastic Surgery*.